

inheritance of breakage components, and would ultimately help in the development of varieties with high head-rice recovery. Agronomists and technicians may use the method to develop recommendations on date of harvest, cultivation practices, drying method, and processing to ensure high head-rice recovery. ■

Microorganisms associated with spotted and discolored rice grains in Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, discoloration of rice grain (i.e. grain spotting) seems to have increased with the cultivation of high yielding varieties and the use of high nitrogen rates. Some varietal and seasonal differences in grain spotting seem to occur. The actual causes of spotting have not been confirmed. Although microorganisms have been found associated with it, pathogens of seedborne diseases could be involved. An attempt was made to isolate and identify the organisms associated with spotted and discolored rice grains. Grains from different varieties were collected at maturity by harvesting intact panicles during 1978 boro, aus, and T. aman at the BRRI farm. The healthy and spotted or discolored grains from each panicle were separated and the percentages of spotted grains per variety were calculated. About 100 spotted grains of each variety were then dehulled.

Unhulled and dehulled grains were then surface-sterilized in 0.5% NaClO for 5 minutes and 3 minutes, respectively, and plated at 10 grains/plate on potato dextrose agar (PDA) and Blotter. The plates were incubated for 10 to 14 days at about 28°C. Microorganisms in the grains grew in about 3 days of incubation. Some were transferred to fresh PDA plates for purification, sporulation, and identification; others were examined directly under the microscope and identified. The total numbers of each type of organism from grains of each variety were then recorded. Twenty microorganisms — 17 fungi, 2 bacteria, and

Microorganisms isolated from spotted and discolored rice grains and the frequency of occurrence in different varieties and seasons in Bangladesh.

Organisms isolated	Occurrence (%) ^a									
	Boro		Aus				T. aman			
	Hbj BII	IR8	Chan- dina	BR3	BR6	BR8	IR20	BR3	BR6	BR8
<i>Acrocyndrium oryzae</i>	—	—	—	3	2	1	—	4	—	5
<i>Aspergillus</i> spp.	6	14	2	2	2	4	—	—	1	—
<i>Cephalosporium</i> sp.	—	—	13	13	25	25	—	—	16	10
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	—	—	2	4	7	3	—	—	—	1
<i>Curvularia lunata</i>	5	3	7	10	16	4	18	9	25	12
<i>Drechslera oryzae</i>	7	6	6	14	10	13	8	15	28	22
<i>Eurotium</i> sp.	1	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Fusarium</i> spp.	1	1	7	8	8	13	11	4	4	10
<i>Nigrospora oryzae</i>	—	—	1	—	—	—	11	—	—	—
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	—	—	5	2	2	5	—	—	—	—
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	—	—	2	—	8	8	—	—	—	—
<i>Pyrenochaeta</i> sp.	—	—	—	2	11	5	—	—	—	—
<i>Trichoconis padwickii</i>	6	5	1	16	22	9	5	38	62	52
Unidentified sp. I	—	—	2	2	5	—	—	—	1	—
" sp. II	—	—	2	—	2	—	—	—	—	—
" sp. III	—	—	1	—	—	—	5	5	—	—
" sp. IV	—	—	1	2	1	2	—	—	—	1
<i>Actinomycetes</i> sp.	5	9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Bacterium</i> (white)	—	—	10	7	10	1	—	—	—	—
<i>Bacterium</i> (yellow)	—	—	14	3	9	41	—	3	4	9
Spotted grains/panicle (%)	6	9	44	55	31	96	54	52	35	61

^aCalculated from total number of colonies appearing among 100 to 200 plated, discolored seeds per variety.

1 actinomycete — were found associated with spotted and discolored grains (see table). The most commonly isolated organisms were *Curvularia lunata*, *Trichoconis padwickii*, *Cephalosporium* sp., *Drechslera oryzae*, *Fusarium* sp., and a yellow bacterium. Those that were isolated from both unhulled and dehulled grains were *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, *D. oryzae*, *T. padwickii*, *Fusarium* sp., *Aspergillus* sp., *Cephalosporium* sp., *C. lunata*, *Chaetomium* sp., unidentified

sp. I and IV, *Actinomycetes* sp., and two bacteria. The first four are the causal agents of sheath rot, brown spot, stack burn, and bakanae diseases. Four of the fungi did not sporulate and hence could not be identified. They were sent to the Commonwealth Mycological Institute for identification. Grain spotting, to which BR8 is susceptible, is lowest during boro. Further work on grain spotting and discoloration is in progress. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Tungro propagation

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A method for propagating tungro-infected rice seedlings and tungro vectors was developed. It consists of 1) rearing tungro vectors *Nephotettix virescens* and providing a tungro source for a constant supply of viruliferous insects, 2) raising

TN1 seedlings in a seedbed covered with improvised wooden cages with metal screens, 3) inoculating the seedlings by releasing viruliferous insects into the cages, and 4) transplanting the seedlings after exposure to the viruliferous insects.

A field prepared as a seedbed was divided into eight sections (see photo). Each section is a plot. 1.3 × 3.8 m, subdivided into three lots, each about 1 × 1 m. Two sections of the seedbed are

Layout of covered seedlings for tungro production. IRRI.

used in each tungro propagation. About 750 g of TN1 seeds are soaked in water on Mondays. The following day, the soaked seeds are sown in 10-row lots individually covered with improvised cages. Fourteen days after seed soaking,

7,000 to 10,000 adult green leafhoppers are given a 4-day acquisition access time on tungro-diseased plants. Then 1,000 to 1,500 viruliferous insects are introduced into each cage for a 11 inoculation access time of 6 days. After

inoculation, the living insects are recovered from each cage to be used to generate new insect colonies. The seedlings are then pulled for transplanting. The procedures of tungro propagation, from seed soaking to transplanting, take 3 weeks. The present schedule is to prepare the seedbed, soak seeds, and confine insects on diseased plants on Mondays; sow on Tuesdays; harvest on Thursdays; and inoculate seedlings on Fridays.

Use of the propagation method results in the deposit of *N. virescens* eggs on 30,000 seedlings/week (5,000 seedlings/lot); more than 90% of the seedlings are infected. In 65 randomized samplings for the hatchability of eggs laid on seedlings, from 0.01 to 13 nymphs/seedling were found, an average of 7 nymphs/seedling. Transmission tests of nymphs randomly collected from the inoculated seedlings indicated that 64% had acquired the tungro virus and were capable of infecting seedlings. ■

Varietal resistance and possible components of horizontal resistance to blast

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Plants of Tetep, Carreon, IR36, IR442, and Khao-tah-haeng 17 (KTH) were inoculated with *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates 7506 and 2017 at 21 days after seeding. The plants had been grown from seed in pots with high-nitrogen soil under 12-hour day/night temperatures of 29°/21°C. Inoculated plants were placed in a dew chamber at 21°C for 24 hours, then transferred to 25°/11°C day/night temperature conditions. Six days after inoculation the lesions and the spores in each lesion were counted. Three-cm-long leaf pieces with only 1 lesion were excised, washed with distilled water, placed in individual humidity chambers made from petri dishes, and incubated

Table 1. Average number of type 3 (T-3) and type 4 (T-4) blast lesions formed on the upper leaf of 30 plants of 5 rice varieties 6 days after inoculation.

Isolate	Lesions (no.)									
	Tetep		Carreon		IR36		IR442		KTH	
	T-3	T-4	T-3	T-4	T-3	T-4	T-3	T-4	T-3	T-4
2017	0.5	3.9	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	1.5	3.4	16.9
7506	0	0	0	0	0	0.6	0	1.6	0.5	4.0

for 77 hours. Each lesion was vigorously washed in 0.5 ml distilled water and spores were counted with a haemocytometer. Each count was replicated 10 times; 5 lesions/isolate and 5 lesions/variety were examined. The lesions were further incubated for another 72 hours, counted, and then

measured.

When inoculated with either isolate Carreon failed to produce symptoms, indicating vertical resistance to both isolates. Tetep expressed vertical resistance to isolate 7506 but was susceptible to 2017. KTH, IR36, and IR441 were susceptible to both

Table 2. Mean size of lesions on leaves of 4 rice varieties 12, 13, 15, and 24 days after inoculation with two blast isolates.

Days after inoculation	Mean lesion size ^a (mm)					
	Isolate 2017			Isolate 7506		
	Tetep	KTH	IR442	IR36	KTH	IR442
12	4.0 × 2.0	6.4 × 2.0	3.0 × 2.1	7.2 × 2.2	10.4 × 3.3	8.0 × 2.3
13	3.8 × 1.6	6.4 × 2.1	3.4 × 2.0	—	—	—
15	10.0 × 1.4	8.1 × 2.0	3.8 × 2.1	—	16.8 × 2.0	15.2 × 2.0
24	12.6 × 1.7	22.2 × 2.2	20.4 × 2.0	—	19.6 × 2.0	—

^aLength × width.